

Corrosion behavior of black steel embedded in BYF cement mortars

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1. Summary: This paper describes a study of the corrosion behavior of black steel reinforcement embedded in mortars made with a belite-ye'elinite-ferrite (BYF) cement, a promising replacement for Portland cement, with a significantly lower carbon footprint. Steel does passivate in BYF mortars, however the corrosion behavior at early ages differs to that of reinforced Portland mortars. The passivation of steel embedded in BYF and Portland mortars is discussed based on the physico-chemical evolution of hydrated cements.

2. Keywords: Steel corrosion, electrochemistry, innovative cement, hydration.

3. Introduction: Different research works have been carried out for several years to diminish the CO₂ emissions of cement manufacturing. A viable lower-carbon alternative to Portland cement is the so-called Belite-Ye'elinite-Ferrite (BYF) cements family. BYF clinker manufacturing requires less limestone in the raw materials, a lower clinkering temperature and less energy to be ground in comparison to Portland clinker. The industrial feasibility was checked and in-situ measurements confirmed CO₂ savings between 25 to 30% (Gartner *et al.*, 2014). The main concern is related to the possibility to embed ordinary black steel reinforcement in BYF-based concrete. The hydration path of BYF cements is quite different to that of Portland ones (Morin *et al.* 2011); hence the evolutions of their pore solution chemistry and pH follow different trends. Thus, the corrosion of embedded steel in BYF matrix remains an area which requires further research. The goal of the present study is to evaluate the corrosion behavior of steel reinforcement embedded in BYF and Portland cement mortars.

4. Experimental methods: The experimental consisted of electrochemical measurements to evaluate the corrosion behavior of steel when embedded in mortars. The BYF cement was composed of 31% of Ye'elinite (C₄A₃\$), 35% of C₂S, 18% Ferrite (C₄AF) and 8% of calcium sulfate, the remaining considered as inert. A CEM I cement was considered as OPC reference (60% C₃S, 18% C₂S, 5% C₃A, 10.5% C₄AF, 3% calcium sulfate). Mortars were made according to the standard NF EN 196-1, with a proportion sand / cement / water of 3 / 1 / 0.5. Additional samples with higher water to cement ratio (0.67) were made. Indeed, BYF cements can require more water to fully hydrate than OPC. To mimic in service conditions, black steel ribbed rebars with mill scale were embedded in BYF and CEM I mortars. The ends of the rebars were coated to minimize edge effect. The final samples, called "lollipops" (see Fig. 1a), were stored at 20°C after casting, demolded 24 hours after mixing and then placed in a humid chamber regulated at 20°C and 90-95% of relative humidity for further hydration. Half-cell measurement and Linear Polarization Resistance method (LPR) were used to evaluate the corrosion behavior as a function of time. Fig. 1b shows the corrosion cell used to carry out electrochemical measurements. Because the cement and its pore solution change during the curing time, multiple techniques to study hydration were employed, such as XRD-Rietveld, TGA and TDA. The pH measurements were carried out in solutions extracted from neat cement pastes.

Figure 1 a) Schematic illustration of the process to produce reinforced mortar specimens and b) Schematic of the test set-up used to carry electrochemical measurements.

5. Results and discussion: Fig. 2 shows the evolution of volume phases composition of hydrated cement pastes as a function of time with: a) CEM I and b) BYF.

Figure 2 Evolution of volume phase composition of hydrated cement pastes as a function of time with: a) CEM I and b) BYF.

The hydrated CEM I cement paste is mainly composed of C-S-H, Portlandite ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$), Ettringite and AFm (calcium monosulfoaluminate and monocarboaluminate). With BYF, the first stage of hydration is the formation of Ettringite, AFm and hydroxide alumina. After two days, Straetlingite (C_2ASH_8) began to form as the reaction product between Ye'elite and aluminium hydroxide. After depletion of aluminium hydroxide (7 days), the main hydrates are Ettringite, AFm, and Straetlingite. Siliceous hydrogarnet (as C_3ASH_4) and C-S-H are present as secondary phases. The results are similar with a water to cement ratio of 0.50 or 0.67. The pH evolution of solutions extracted from neat pastes is shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Evolution of the pH of the solutions extracted from OPC and BYF neat pastes.

pH measurements taken from neat cement paste extracts			
Hydration time	OPC (w/c = 0.50)	BYF (w/c = 0.50)	BYF (w/c = 0.67)
5 minutes	13.2	10.6	10.7
28 days	13.3	13.0	13.0

Fig. 3 shows the half-cell potentials, $E_{\text{half-cell}}$, and the corrosion current density, j_{corr} , evolution as function of the hydration of OPC and BYF mortars.

Figure 3 Evolution of **a)** half-cell potentials and **b)** corrosion current density as a function of time for reinforced OPC and BYF mortars.

For the three types of samples, the half-cell potential values increase during the three months of investigation, sharply the first days and then more slowly (cf. Fig 3a). The threshold value (-126 mV/SCE) corresponding to a low risk of corrosion according to the ASTM C876 (ASTM International, 2009), is reached after 14 days with CEM I mortars. This value is reached later with BYF-based samples. But as this threshold is relative to OPC-based matrix, we cannot conclude if the corrosion risk is really higher with BYF. We then have to consider the corrosion rate that can be evaluated with the current density j_{corr} . The current density strongly decreased between 1 and 14 days of hydration (Fig. 3b). The curves corresponding to the CEM I and BYF samples made with a water to cement ratio of 0.50 are very similar. The values of j_{corr} for BYF samples made with a water to cement ratio of 0.67 are greater during the first 28 days of hydration and are finally very close to those of the other two types of samples. According to the RILEM recommendations (Andrade *et al.*, 2004), values of j_{corr} below 0.1 $\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$ correspond to "passivation". Values between 0.1 and 0.2 $\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$ correspond to a transition between passive and active corrosion. Figure 3.b) shows that it takes 7 days of hydration for the current density to drop to values below 0.2 $\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$ when steel is embedded in BYF mortars, compared to only 2 days with OPC. However, the actual amount of corrosion occurring during this initial period is negligible. To date (up to 6 months) steel remains passivated in both BYF and OPC matrices.

5. Conclusions: It took seven days of hydration for the corrosion rate to drop to very low values in the BYF mortars, compared to only two days with OPC. Considering a more conservative criteria ($j_{\text{corr}} < 0.1 \mu\text{A}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$), 14 and 28 days are required to assure passivation of black steel in OPC and BYF mortar, respectively. The delay for BYF mortars can be explained with the lower pH during the first hours of hydration. Despite the difference of composition of the hydrated pastes, the pH was finally basic with BYF and CEM I and the current corrosion rate similar corresponding to a passive state after 28 days.

6. References:

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